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IDIOPATHIC PHOTOSENSITIVE OCCIPITAL EPILEPSY – A CASE REPORT

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Uvod: Idiopathic photosensitive occipital epilepsy is a type of reflex epilepsy in which a flashing lights or contrasting light and dark patterns bring on the seizures. It is a benign childhood epilepsy, with usually normal neuroradiological findings. They are usually presented with visual hallucinations, amblyopia, myoclonic movements, but they can also present like secondary generalized seizure.

Cilj rada: In order to further understand this type of epilepsy, we represented a pediatric case of idiopathic photosensitive occipital epilepsy.

Materijal i metode: We reviewed the medical chart of a patient admitted to Pediatric Clinic in Novi Sad. Written informed consent for the publication of the case description was obtained.

Rezultati: A 11 years old girl was hospitalized to Pediatric Clinic due to generalized seizure which happened while she was watching television. Physical and neurological examination did not show any pathological signs. Magnetic resonance imaging was described as normal. The neurophysiological test showed a normal background activity, isolated occipital spike and waves and photoparoxysmal response (generalized polyspike/spike and waves) during the 15-Hz and 50Hz intermittent photic stimulation. Antiepileptic therapy was not introduced, she was discharged with an advice to avoid the provoking factors. The follow up period for our patient was 2 years, and by that time, she did not have any seizures.

Zaključak: Reflex seizures induced by different stimuli should be questioned during the evaluation of the patients with seizure disorders, and when necessary, stimulations during electrophysiological studies may be performed for correct diagnosis. A careful history taking to identify environmental precipitating factors is essential to make a proper diagnosis of reflex epilepsy. Avoiding the specific trigger is particularly important for prevention of seizures. Comprehensive knowledge of pediatricians can help to avoid unnecessary diagnostics tests, and usage of anticonvulsants.

Ključne reči: reflex epilepsy, photosensitivity, case report